

OCEAN:ICE News – September 2023

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome Back from the Summer of 2023

Dear OCEAN:ICE Friends,

We hope that everyone has enjoyed their summers and has had time to relax and re-energize for the rest of the year. We cannot start this month's newsletter without addressing the events of summer 2023. This summer has been like no other. Across the globe, people have experienced extremes – from rampant wildfires in Canada and Hawaii to scorching heatwaves sweeping through Southern Europe. Against this backdrop, the words of UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres echo loudly in our minds: ["The era of global warming has ended; the era of global boiling has arrived"](#).

For the researchers of OCEAN:ICE, this summer has also brought a series of peculiar events that have raised concerns and highlighted uncertainties amongst the research community. While Antarctica may often seem distant and disconnected from the everyday lives of many across the globe, [the historic lows of sea ice extent coupled](#) with the experiences on the ground of people around the world has bridged that gap, bringing the Southern continent closer to home.

For the UK Grant Coordinator, Andrew Meijers, these occurrences have brought forth a pressing question, "Is the climate crisis finally catching up with Antarctica?". In his recent op-ed for The Guardian, [Andrew Meijers](#) shed light on the significant role played by Antarctica and the Southern Ocean within the broader context of climate

change, particularly considering the historic lows in Antarctic Sea ice and the uncertainties of future evolution and impacts on the global climate and population. Projections of Antarctica's ice melt's contributions to rising sea levels remains riddled in uncertainty, underscoring the urgency to increase our confidence in these forecasts through improving our understanding of ocean and ice processes. These summer months have highlighted the significance and urgency of the work we are undertaking in OCEAN:ICE for the EU and globally.

As we approach autumn, we are gearing up to accelerate our efforts, coinciding with our first-year anniversary in October at the Annual Project Meeting in Paris, in collaboration with the EU Horizon 2020 project, SO-CHIC. Parallely, we are preparing for our policy briefing set to take place in early 2024, in collaboration with the EU Horizon 2020 project, ARCTIC PASSION. More to come on this in the future! For now, enjoy this month's September OCEAN:ICE newsletter.

Catching up on August

OCEAN:ICE at SOOS Symposium in Hobart

Last month, the [OCEAN:ICE team headed down South to the SOOS Symposium 2023 in Hobart, Tasmania](#). Our involvement was marked by achievements, with Andrew Meijers leading the plenary presentation on Southern Ocean observations, addressing both the current state and future prospects. His talk also emphasized the crucial circumpolar observational plan and its integration with ice sheet modelling, a focal point of the OCEAN:ICE project.

Joining Andrew were fellow OCEAN:ICE members, Markus Janout, Pierre Detrieux, Povl Abrahamsen, and Antonio Novellini, who captured some moments from Andrew's presentation.

Notably, OCEAN:ICE left its impact through the session, 'Circumpolar Antarctic Ice Sheet-Ocean Observations: Towards an Integrated Perspective and Enhanced Climate Models'. This session, co-convened by Andrew Meijers, Markus Janout, Pierre Dutrieux in collaboration with Felicity McCormack from Monash University and Sue Cook from the University of Tasmania, successfully brought together scientists from around the world.

The session revolved around OCEAN:ICE's core theme of coordinated circumpolar observations, aiming to better understand the delivery and export of waters to key regions of ocean and ice-sheet interaction. The session also provided understanding of the specific observations required and the regions where they are most critical to support modelling efforts in this region.

Read our full article [here](#).

OCEAN:ICE has a New Look!

Our revamped [OCEAN:ICE website](#) launched this August. Have you explored it yet?

Don't know where to start? Let us give you some suggestions:

The Knowledge Hub

Head over to the OCEAN:ICE [Knowledge Hub](#) where you can find resources to learn about the project and share with others. Here you can find [articles where OCEAN:ICE has been in the news](#), [OCEAN:ICE Breakers](#), [Factsheets and Infographics](#), and [Webinars](#).

Events

Keep track of our [events](#) where OCEAN:ICE will and have been!

Here you can also find our [Climate Coffee](#) series where we bring in researchers to discuss their work and latest findings.

We've made it simple for you to keep tabs on our whereabouts and upcoming events. Use our [calendar](#) to sync our events with your schedule, ensuring you never miss out on anything.

Happening this month

Climate Coffee with Romain Millan

The premiere of the [Climate Coffee](#) series kicks off this month. Catch [Romain Millan](#) (CNRS) for his Climate Coffee on 'Monitoring ice shelf vulnerability from multiple sensor remote sensing data'. Romain takes the stage on Thursday, September 21, 2023 from 10:00 to 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Romain Millan, CNRS

Monitoring ice shelf vulnerability at both poles from multiple sensor remote sensing data

21 September 2023 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

OCEANICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- **11 – 14 September 2023, [SCAR INSTANT](#), Trieste (IT)**
- **3 – 5 October 2023, [10th EuroGOOS International Conference](#), Galway (IR)**
- **9 – 13 October 2023, [Ocean Practices: OBPS Workshop VII](#), Online**
- **16 October 2023, [TiPPACS World Café](#), Brussels (BE)**

- **23 – 26 October 2023, [OCEAN:ICE x SO-CHIC Annual Partner Meeting](#), Paris (FR)**

Upcoming Climate Coffees

Register for the upcoming [Climate Coffees](#) for 2023 [here](#).

- 21 September 2023, Climate Coffee with [Romain Millan \(CNRS\)](#) on Monitoring ice shelf vulnerability from multiple sensor remote sensing data
- 16 November 2023, Climate Coffee with [Mark Payne \(DMI\)](#) on An Experiment in Climate Service Portability: Implementing a Danish Climate Atlas in Ghana

- 7 December 2023, Climate Coffee with [Shenjie Zhou](#) (BAS) on [Slowdown of Antarctic Bottom Water export driven by climatic wind and sea-ice changes](#)
- 14 December 2023, Climate Coffee with Kathryn Gunn (University of Southampton) on [Recent reduced abyssal overturning and ventilation in the Australian Antarctic Basin](#)

Climate Coffee

Early Career Highlights

Apply for the Southern Ocean Summer School 2024

The applications for the [Southern Ocean Summer School 2024](#) in Cargese, Corsica are still open. Start preparing your application now and send it in before 31 October 2023.

APPLICATIONS ARE OPEN!

The Southern Ocean Summer School 2024

7 - 18 May 2024

Institut d'Études Scientifiques de Cargèse
Corsica, France

Apply by 31 October 2023

The Southern Ocean Summer School 2024 will be hosted in Corsica, in the small village of Cargèse, at the [Institut d'Études Scientifiques de Cargèse \(IESC\)](#). SOSS 2024 provides a unique opportunity for research master students, graduate students, and first-year postdocs to dive into the fascinating world of Southern Ocean sciences. This intensive program is designed to expand your knowledge and deepen your understanding of this crucial region of the world.

Researcher in the Spotlight: Introducing Shenjie Zhou

We have continued with our article series. Researcher in the Spotlight. Last month, we interviewed Shenjie Zhou, an incoming member of the OCEAN:ICE team and an early-career scientist.

Check out his interview [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

That's all for this month's newsletter.

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<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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